

Experience the Extraordinary

2014 ATLA Annual Conference

American Theological Library Association
Hosted by the New Orleans Baptist Theological Seminary

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*Richard Thompson, Professor of New Testament
Northwest Nazarene University*

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Let's Experience the Extraordinary

Welcome to the 2014 ATLA Annual Conference! This year's conference brings together a wealth of educational programs, interest group meetings, excursions, and events set in the rich culture and heritage of the French Quarter.

The InterContinental New Orleans is perfectly situated in downtown, with convenient access to the French Quarter's diverse cuisine, museums, shopping, and attractions.

Our opening reception will take place at our hotel, the InterContinental New Orleans, in its new time slot of 6:00 p.m. - 7:30 p.m. Enjoy drinks and light hors d'oeuvres with an opportunity to reconnect with your colleagues before heading out to explore New Orleans's many restaurants and attractions.

The local host committee will be especially excited to welcome you to our campus, the New Orleans Baptist Theological Seminary, for an afternoon of learning and an evening of celebration on Friday, June 20.

Experience the Extraordinary! We invite you to learn more about the 2014 ATLA Annual Conference in this program book.

-2014 Local Host Committee, New Orleans Baptist Theological Seminary (NOBTS)

FROM THE LOCAL HOST

LOCAL HOST COMMITTEE

(Back, left to right) Eric Benoy, Dr. Jeff Griffin, (Front, left to right) Cindy Ennis, Kyara St. Amant, Michele McClellan

CONFERENCE COMMITTEE

Tracy Powell Iwaskow (chair), Ky St. Amant, Eric Benoy, Suzanne Estelle-Holmer, Lisa Grover, Liz Leahy, Michelle Spomer, Stephen Sweeney

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Welcome	1-3
Navigating the Conference	4-6
Conference Highlights	7
Conference Schedules	
Tuesday & Wednesday	9-10
Thursday	11-17
At-a-Glance	11
Daily Schedule	12-17
Friday	18-22
At-a-Glance	18
Daily Schedule	18-22
Saturday	23-26
At-a-Glance	23
Daily Schedule	23-26
Exhibits	27-30

MOBILE SCHEDULE

For up-to-the minute updates and more!

LANYRD.COM/CTPPW

New from Bloomsbury and T&T Clark

Visit our booth for 35% off

A Textbook of Christian Ethics

Robin Gill
592 pp | PB 9780567595928 | \$42.95 \$28.00

An Introduction to Christian Theology

Anthony Towey
560 pp | PB 9780567045355 | \$39.95 \$26.00

Ask the Beasts

Darwin and the God of Love
Elizabeth A. Johnson
352 pp | HB 9781472903730 | \$32.95 \$21.00

Conscience and Calling

Ethical Reflections on Catholic Women's Church Vocations
Anne E. Patrick
224 pp | PB 9781441144522 | \$24.95 \$16.00

Filled with all the Fullness of God

An Introduction to Catholic Spirituality
Thomas McDermott, OP
128 pp | PB 9780567341976 | \$24.95 \$16.00

Found Theology

History, Imagination and the Holy Spirit
Ben Quash
336 pp | PB 9780567517920 | \$34.95 \$23.00

In Search of Authority

Anglican Theological Method from the Reformation to the Enlightenment
Paul Avis
416 pp | PB 9780567026484 | \$34.95 \$23.00

Levinas and Theology

Nigel Zimmermann
208 pp | PB 9780567248671 | \$24.95 \$16.00

Merleau-Ponty and Theology

Christopher Ben Simpson
272 pp | PB 9780567217677 | \$27.95 \$16.00

Newman and his Family

Edward Short
448 pp | PB 9780567104342 | \$34.95 \$23.00

On Animals, Volume I

Systematic Theology
David L. Clough
240 pp | PB 9780567632869 | \$34.95 \$23.00

Reading the Liturgy

An exploration of texts in Christian worship
Juliette J. Day
192 pp | PB 9780567063359 | \$29.95 \$19.00

Scripture

A Guide for the Perplexed
William R S Lamb
224 pp | PB 9780567514097 | \$25.95 \$17.00

T&T Clark Companion to Nonconformity

Ed. Robert Pope and D. Denisil Morgan
768 pp | HB 9780567505262 | \$175.00 \$114.00

The God Argument

The Case Against Religion and for Humanism
A. C. Grayling
288 pp | PB 9781620401927 | \$17.00 \$11.00

The T&T Clark Companion to Augustine and Modern Theology

Ed. C. C. Pecknold and Tarmo Toom
304 pp | HB 9780567033819 | \$160.00 \$104.00

B L O O M S B U R Y

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The Annual Conference and Local Host Committees and ATLA staff have put together an outstanding conference experience for you! The sessions reflect the broad spectrum of knowledge and skills that today's theological librarians are expected to cover – everything from technology to the literature of religion and theology to implementing RDA and handling archival materials. There's truly something for everyone!

We are especially excited about this year's plenary sessions, which are focused on the future. Joseph P. Lucia, Dean, Temple University Libraries, will reflect on guiding principles that can help libraries transform themselves into newly vital spaces in the digital age and Kathryn Reklis, Assistant Professor, Department of Theology at Fordham University will look at the promises and challenges of new media in the academic study of religion. Both of these presentations promise to be both thought provoking and inspiring on many levels.

Be sure to join us for the ATLA Business Meeting on Thursday to participate in an open forum on the proposed member dues increases and the Association update on Friday for further conversations on our work together.

The conference would not be possible without the support of our exhibitors and sponsors so please be sure to stop by and talk with them about their products and services in the exhibit hall on Thursday and Friday.

The ATLA Annual Conference is always an opportunity to greet old friends, to make new ones, and to expand your professional connections. Please be sure to introduce yourself to new members and first-time attendees – there are over 30 of them this year – and give them a warm ATLA welcome!

We look forward to seeing all of you throughout the conference.

Learn and enjoy!

A LETTER FROM THE PRESIDENT & EXECUTIVE DIRECTOR

BETH BIDLACK
ATLA PRESIDENT

BRENDA BAILEY-HAINER
ATLA EXECUTIVE DIRECTOR

SOCIAL MEDIA AT A GLANCE

#ATLA2014

@YOURATLA

NAVIGATING THE CONFERENCE

ON-SITE REGISTRATION HOURS

LOCATED ON THIRD FLOOR OPPOSITE GRAND STAIRCASE

TUESDAY, JUNE 17	12:00 P.M. – 7:00 P.M.
WEDNESDAY, JUNE 18	7:00 A.M. – 7:30 P.M.
THURSDAY, JUNE 19	7:00 A.M. – 7:00 P.M.
FRIDAY, JUNE 20	7:00 A.M. – 3:30 P.M.
SATURDAY, JUNE 21	7:00 A.M. – 10:30 A.M.

EXHIBIT HALL HOURS

LOCATED AT LA SALLE A & LE SALON ON THE THIRD FLOOR

THURSDAY, JUNE 19	10:00 A.M. – 6:00 P.M.
FRIDAY, JUNE 20	8:45 A.M. – 3:30 P.M.

NAVIGATING THE CONFERENCE

LOCATION OF SESSIONS

Intercontinental New Orleans
444 Saint Charles Ave
New Orleans, LA 70130
T: 504.525.5566

New Orleans Baptist Theological
Seminary
3939 Gentilly Blvd
New Orleans, LA 70126
T: 800.662.8701

Conference sessions and meetings Tuesday through Sunday will be held at the InterContinental New Orleans. Exceptions include excursions, hosted dinners, and Friday tour of New Orleans Baptist Theological Seminary (NOBTS), worship, and plenary session.

NEW ORLEANS GUIDE

Scan the QR Code for a list of the top restaurants to eat in New Orleans, attractions, and stores. Check out the Local Host Welcome Table at La Salle Foyer for more suggestions.

▽ REGISTRATION

⚡ LOCAL HOST
WELCOME TABLE

The New Orleans Dining Guide.
Please scan the QR Code or go to
<http://kaywa.me/u4pel>.

INTERCONTINENTAL.
NEW ORLEANS

Third Floor

Meeting Rooms

- Acadian Rooms I & II
- Fulton Room
- La Salle Ballrooms A, B & C
- La Salle Pre-Function Area
- Le Salon Pre-Function Area
- Pelican Rooms I & II
- Pelican Pre-Function Area
- Poydras Room

Advantage Office

Second Floor

Meeting Rooms

- Audubon Boardroom
- Les Continents
- Cypress Room
- Lobby Conference Room
- Magnolia Room
- Oak Room

- Lobby Bar
- Concierge & Business Center
- Guest Registration
- Guest Relations
- Veranda Restaurant
- Zachary Taylor Room

Ground Floor

Meeting Rooms

- Cabildo Room
- Orleans Room
- Pontalba Room
- Vieux Carré Rooms A & B

- Advantage Office
- Baggage Check-In
- Gift Shop
- Pete's Bar & Grill
- Sweet Car

*UNRENOVATED FLOOR PLAN

NAVIGATING THE CONFERENCE

INDEX OF COMMON GROUPS AND NAMES

FUNNEL PROJECTS

NACO - Name Authority Cooperative Program of the Program for Cooperative Cataloging (PCC)

CONSER - Cooperative Online Serials Program of the Program for Cooperative Cataloging (PCC)

INTEREST GROUPS

CEAD - Collection Evaluation and Development

CUIG - College and University

ETIG - Emerging Technology

PSIG - Public Services

SCIG - Special Collections

TLIG - Teaching and Learning

TSIG - Technical Services

WCIG - World Christianity

WRIG - World Religions

PHOTOGRAPHY AND RECORDING

There may be photography, audio, or video recording at the conference. Photographs/recordings taken at the ATLA Conference may be used in future marketing, publicity, promotions, advertising, and training activities for ATLA. By entering the event premises, you agree to allow ATLA to use the photographs/video – which may include you – in all media formats worldwide. If you do not want to be photographed or videotaped, please notify the photographer or recorder and we will gladly adhere to your request.

SESSION FORMATS

CONVERSATION GROUPS - presenter(s) gives brief introductory remarks (no longer than 10 minutes) and facilitates a discussion among participants.

PRE-CONFERENCE AND IN-CONFERENCE WORKSHOPS - workshop leaders operate in a classroom environment to deliver training on a specific topic.

INTEREST GROUP PRESENTATIONS - can include a range of activities from papers to panels to on-site field trips.

LISTEN AND LEARN SESSIONS - session leader(s) presents on a topic that provides practical training and introduces attendees to products/ideas or best/current practices.

PANEL PRESENTATIONS - a moderator and panelists present a topic or the results of research to the audience.

PAPERS - a single presenter reads a paper or presents research to the audience.

POSTER SESSIONS - sessions are informal; presenter(s) develops posters and handouts which deliver useful information to the theological library community.

SOCIAL MEDIA

The official conference hashtag is #ATLA2014. Follow ATLA on Facebook at www.facebook.com/AmericanTheologicalLibraryAssociation and on Twitter at www.twitter.com/YourATLA.

Enjoy taking photos? Share your New Orleans photos and tag them #ATLA2014 on Instagram and Flickr! Follow ATLA on Flickr at www.flickr.com/photos/YourATLA for more conference images.

WELCOMERS, NEW MEMBERS, AND FIRST-TIME ATTENDEES

The ATLA Annual Conference provides an excellent opportunity to reconnect with colleagues and forge new friendships with professionals from across the country and around the world.

Attendees who have signed up as Welcomers have volunteered to help New Members and First-Time Attendees make connections and maximize the conference experience for everyone. Welcomers are identifiable by their Welcomer ribbons, available at the registration desk. Welcomers are not paired with a specific attendee, but instead are available to welcome all new and first-time attendees who may need help. Thanks to all of the Welcomers for helping to make the conference an inviting experience for everyone.

New Member and First-Time Attendee ribbons will be available at registration. New Members and First Time Attendees are invited to wear these ribbons so that other attendees can make sure to introduce themselves and provide a friendly ATLA welcome.

Welcomers, New Members, and First-Time Attendees can make their first connections at the President's Welcome Reception and continue the conversation throughout the conference.

THURSDAY, JUNE 19 **9:00 A.M. - 10:00 A.M.**

Common Ends: Libraries, Imagination, & the Conflict of Values in the Digital Moment

For the better part of two decades, libraries have been subject to a series of “end times” narratives, the visions therein always premised upon the waning of print culture and the eventual demise of the physical book as an embodiment of knowledge and culture. In parallel to those apocalyptic narratives, there’s been a counter-trend that celebrates the renaissance of the library as a newly vital space – liberated from the constraints of physical collections and devoted to the discovery and creation of new knowledge and culture. This talk will examine both the anxiety and the promise within those conflicting visions and posits in response a set of abiding principles that can guide us toward a medium independent understanding of library mission at a moment when transformation is a reality not just a buzzword.

Joseph P. Lucia is Dean of University Libraries at Temple University, a system of nine libraries, including branches in Japan and Rome, and the Temple University Press. Lucia has experience managing development campaigns, overseeing new library facilities, developing open source discovery software, creating substantial digital libraries, and establishing open access publishing initiatives. Lucia served as University Librarian and Director of the Falvey Memorial Library at Villanova University, from 2002 to 2013. Falvey Library was the recipient of the 2013 Excellence in Academic Libraries Award from the Association of College and Research Libraries (ACRL).

Location: La Salle BC

FRIDAY, JUNE 20 **4:45 P.M. - 5:45 P.M.**

Tweet if You Want Tenure? New Media and the “New Academy”

Amidst concerns about the “decline of the liberal arts” and demands to make academic research and teaching more relevant to the real world are parallel prophecies of a “new academy” - one driven by new technologies of the digital age. Some greet the digital with eschatological hope, some with apocalyptic doom. Drawing on both her experiences using digital platforms in her scholarship and teaching, and her research studying the use of digital technologies by Christian communities, Kathryn Reklis will discuss the promises and challenges of new media in the academic study of religion.

Kathryn Reklis is Assistant Professor of Modern Protestant Theology at Fordham University in New York City. She holds a PhD in religious studies from Yale University, where she concentrated in historical and constructive Christian theology. Her first book, *Theology and the Kinesthetic Imagination: Jonathan Edwards and the Making of Modernity* (Oxford University Press, 2014) explores the intersection of theology and performance studies to investigate the role of the body, desire, and beauty as sources for theological knowledge in the making of modernity. The project engages the colonial puritan theologian Jonathan Edwards and his writings about ecstatic bodily experience of the divine. Through this work she has fallen in love with the eighteenth century and the invention of global gossip culture made possible by a great communications revolution in daily newspapers and widespread pamphlets.

Location: Leavell Chapel ♦

PLENARY SPEAKERS

Don’t miss these notable professionals in the fields of librarianship and religious studies.

JOSEPH P. LUCIA
Dean, Temple University
Libraries

KATHRYN REKLIS
Assistant Professor,
Department of Theology
at Fordham University

Philosophy, Theology
and the Sciences

Volume 1
Number 1
2014

Naturalism
Wesley J. Wildman
Religious Naturalism: What It Can Be, and What It Need Not Be 7-36
Edward Blum
Chinese Qi-Naturalism and Liberal Naturalism 37-63
Thomas Römer
Tracking Jesus' "Centers": Jesus Traditions Inside and Outside the Hebrew Bible 64-76
James Kugel
The Figure of Moses in Job 77-92
Carl S. Ehrlich
"Strangely" Missing: A Decade of Moses Scholarship 2000-2009 93-110

New Projects
Ina Kambik, *Neuere Forschungen zur Archäologie in Subhänien* 113-112
Israel Finkelstein et al., *Reconstructing Ancient Israel: Integrating Macro and Micro Archaeology* 113-110

Philosophy, Theology and the
Sciences (PTSc)

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Announcement of a new journal

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Editors: Celia Deane-Drummond, Dirk Evers,
Niels H. Gregersen, Gregory R. Peterson

Managing Editor: Dirk Evers

Associate Editors: Conor Cunningham, David Fergusson,
Agustín Fuentes, Peter Harrison, Kristian Köchy,
Nancey Murphy, Robert J. Russell, Mikael Stenmark,
Günter Thomas, Wesley Wildman, Gayle E. Woloschak

Philosophy, Theology and the Sciences is a new peer-reviewed biannual journal which provides a platform for constructive and critical interactions between the natural sciences in all their varieties (from physics and biology to psychology, anthropology and social science) and the fields of contemporary philosophy and theology. It invites scholars, religious or non-religious, to participate in that endeavor. The journal provides the rare opportunity to examine together the truth claims found in theology, philosophy, and the sciences, as well as the methods found in each disciplines and the meanings derived from them. Each issue will have a topical focus. The first four issues will be on "Naturalism", "Human Nature and Evolution", "Neuroscience and Morality", and "Contingency".

Find more information at www.mohr.de/ptsc

First issue of Philosophy, Theology and the Sciences

PTSc Volume 1, Number 1, 2014

(will be published in April 2014)

Editorial Manifesto

Naturalism

Varieties of Naturalism and Religious Reflection

Holmes Rolston III: Creative Genesis. Escalating Naturalism and Beyond

Wesley J. Wildman: Religious Naturalism: What It Can Be, and What It Need Not Be

JeeLoo Liu: Chinese Qi-Naturalism and Liberal Naturalism

Charles Taliaferro: Is Naturalism Too Big to Fail? An Audit of Strict and Broad Naturalism

Niels Henrik Gregersen: Naturalism in the Mirror of Religion. Three Theological Options

Book Reviews

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DAILY SCHEDULE

TUESDAY

8:00 A.M. - 12 NOON

ATLA Board of Directors Meeting

Location: Poydras

MEETING

2:00 P.M. - 4:00 P.M.

New Orleans School of Cooking

\$26 per person

Join us for an "Open Demonstration" class in which you will witness a cooking demonstration on how to make the day's selected recipes: Corn & Crab Bisque, Chicken Etouffee, and Pralines. Participants will walk away with copies of the recipe, and a full meal of New Orleans' cuisine.

Location: Refer to ticket

EXCURSION

7:00 P.M. - 9:00 P.M.

INTEREST GROUP PRESENTATION

TSIG: Top Concerns for Technical Services Staff

What are your top concerns in Technical Services? In an open conversation discussing top concerns for Technical Services personnel, participants are especially encouraged to share their experiences with and solutions for clearly and persuasively demonstrating to administration the resources needed for a high-quality end-product as it pertains to a sufficient technical services staff; the wide spectrum of work involved; and the necessity of on-going training in this rapidly-changing environment. Related concerns will include but are not limited to: RDA; e-book acquisitions & cataloging workflows; WorldShare authority work; and, effects of staff reduction.

Presenter: Donna R. Campbell, Technical Services & Systems Librarian, Westminster Theological Seminary

Location: Fulton

WEDNESDAY

8:00 A.M. - 4:30 P.M.

Creating the Leaders of Tomorrow Program

**Special Enrollment Required*

Location: Acadian II

SPECIAL SESSION

8:30 A.M. - 4:30 P.M.

Disaster Preparedness and Recovery

This workshop will provide steps for dealing with emergency incidents from building emergencies to regional disasters, including development of a disaster plan, assessing institutional risks, dealing with mold and pests, mitigation and response, working with disaster recovery vendors, collaborative disaster planning, and disaster recovery resources. In addition, the session will explore basic disaster planning for digital collections. The class includes a building walk-through exercise and recovery demonstrations.

Presenter: Tom Claresson, LYRASIS

Location: Fulton

PRE-CONFERENCE

8:30 A.M. - 12:00 NOON

Prezipalooza: Creating Engaging & Distinctive Presentations

Ever get tired of PowerPoint and Keynote? Prezi software is free, social, and creative. Use Prezi to create unique presentations for instruction, meetings, conferences, and more. Attendees will learn the basics of designing a Prezi, and will create one by the end of the session. Participants should bring laptop computers to the session and sign up for a Prezi account (<http://prezi.com/pricing/edu>) before the workshop.

Presenter: Michelle Spomer, Head of Stamps Library, Azusa Pacific University

Location: Pelican II

PRE-CONFERENCE

TUESDAY, JUNE 17 - WEDNESDAY, JUNE 18

8:30 A.M. - 12:00 NOON

Programming for Librarians I

Why should librarians know how to program? Knowing a bit of programming can help a librarian or staff member analyze ILS reports, collate data, create reports from "messy" formats like HTML, and even do some "digital humanities" type analysis. In this morning session, participants will learn some of the basics of computational thinking and elements common to almost all programs. We will then talk about different types of programming language and introduce Python. We will cover basic Python commands and concepts, including variables, assignment, and simple programs.

These workshops are appropriate for those with no programming experience. Participants who attended last year's half-day workshop may want to sign-up for the afternoon only. Participants must bring their own laptop to the workshop (PC or Mac).

Presenter: Matthew Collins, Director of the Library and Associate Professor, Louisville Presbyterian Theological Seminary

Location: Acadian I

PRE-CONFERENCE

9:00 A.M. - 11:00 P.M.

Cemetery & Voodoo Walking Tour

\$36 per person

Join us as we walk through St. Louis Cemetery #1, the site of the classic movie *Easy Rider*. Visit the tomb of Marie Laveau – Voodoo Queen of New Orleans. Learn about New Orleans' unique above-ground burial customs and the tombs of various "societies" in this historic cemetery that first opened in 1789. The tour includes climate controlled transportation to and from cemetery and guided tour.

Location: Refer to ticket

EXCURSION

9:00 A.M. - 2:00 P.M.

Oak Alley Plantation

\$52 per person

Explore 25 acres of historic grounds and take a guided tour of the "Big House" at the Oak Alley Plantation. Learn about the impact the Civil War had on this region by visiting the Civil War Encampment Exhibit. Visit the reconstructed slave quarters and tour the exhibit "Slavery at Oak Alley." Breakfast and lunch are available for purchase from Oak Alley Restaurant.

Location: Refer to ticket

EXCURSION

10:00 A.M. - 2:00 P.M.

National World War II Museum

\$22 per person

Join us for a tour of the National WWII Museum, an experience that tells the story of the American Experience in the war that changed the world. The campus includes the Louisiana Memorial Pavilion, showcasing the large artifacts of the war and exhibits on D-Day at Normandy, the Home Front and the Pacific; the Solomon Victory Theater, a 4-D theater showing the exclusive Tom Hanks production, *Beyond All Boundaries* (30 min.); the Stage Door Canteen, where the music and entertainment of the "Greatest Generation" comes to life; the John E. Kushner Restoration Pavilion, where staff and volunteers restore artifacts in public view; and the new U.S. Freedom Pavilion: The Boeing Center, where exhibits

EXCURSION

and interactive experiences paint the picture of a nation mobilized for war. Lunch on your own can be eaten in the American Sector Restaurant or Soda Shop.

Location: Refer to ticket

10:00 A.M. – 12:30 P.M.

EXCURSION

New Orleans School of Cooking
\$29 per person

Join us for an “Open Demonstration” class in which you will witness a cooking demonstration on how to make the day’s selected recipes: Gumbo, Jambalaya, Bread Pudding, and Pralines. Participants will walk away with copies of the recipe, and a full meal of New Orleans’ cuisine.

Location: Refer to ticket

1:00 P.M. – 4:30 P.M.

PRE-CONFERENCE

Establishing Access Points According to RDA in Bibliographic Records

This workshop will give an introduction to RDA heading construction. It is intended for non-NACO cataloguers. We will look at the basic structure of an RDA authority record, highlighting the numerous new fields. We will give a basic introduction to the major changes to headings in RDA. Some examples include the use of profession or occupation to differentiate previously undifferentiated personal names; changes in the addition of titles to personal names; changes in date format with personal names; use of ‘Selections’ with uniform titles; handling of multi-language uniform titles (e.g., English & Greek, Polyglot); and the use of \$i in more fields and more extensively.

Presenter: Judy Knop, Metadata Curator, ATLA; Denise M. Pakala, Associate Librarian for Technical Services, Covenant Theological Seminary

Location: Pelican II

1:00 P.M. – 4:30 P.M.

PRE-CONFERENCE

Programming for Librarians II

Why should librarians know how to program? Knowing a bit of programming can help a librarian or staff member analyze ILS reports, collate data, create reports from “messy” formats like HTML, and even do some “digital humanities” type analysis. This afternoon session will do a quick review of the morning and then introduce simple program loops, searching, text processing, and file input/output routines. We will also cover importing modules and defining functions. Participants will then work on a simple example (or two) that shows how this might work in a library. Resources for further learning will be discussed.

These workshops are appropriate for those with no programming experience. Participants who attended last year’s half-day workshop may want to sign-up for the afternoon only. Participants must bring their own laptop to the workshop (PC or Mac).

Presenter: Matthew Collins, Director of the Library and Associate Professor, Louisville Presbyterian Theological Seminary

Location: Acadian I

4:30 P.M. – 6:00 P.M.

ATLA Choir Rehearsal

Location: Vieux Carré A

5:00 P.M. – 6:00 P.M.

President’s Welcome Reception for New Members and First-Time Attendees // *Invitation Only

Location: Pelican I

6:00 P.M. – 7:30 P.M.

Opening Reception at the InterContinental New Orleans

The perfect starter to your evening! Enjoy light hors d’oeuvres and drinks and reconnect with colleagues before exploring New Orleans. Be sure to check out the New Orleans Dining Guide (page 4) for helpful recommendations on places to eat.

Location: La Salle BC

7:30 P.M. – 8:30 P.M.

ATLA Products – Dessert, Discussion, and Meet and Greet with Maria Stanton, New Director of Production

Join the ATLA products leadership team after the opening reception for a brief and informal discussion of ATLA’s products, followed by Q&A and discussion. Come meet and greet Maria Stanton, ATLA’s new Director of Production, and other product team representatives.

Maria, along with Margot Lyon, Director of Business Development, and Gregg Taylor, Licensing Manager, will discuss current and future developments and opportunities for ATLA products. You are welcome to e-mail your questions ahead of time to products@atla.com, or you are welcome to schedule a personal meeting at the conference with Margot Lyon (mlyon@atla.com), Maria Stanton (mstanton@atla.com) or Gregg Taylor (gtaylor@atla.com). A light dessert will be served. The presentation will be brief, allowing you time for your evening plans. We look forward to seeing you there. RSVPs requested to Rick Rybak (rrybak@atla.com).

Presenters: Margot Lyon, Director of Business Development; Maria Stanton, Director of Production; Gregg Taylor, Licensing Manager

Location: Pelican I

THURSDAY, JUNE 19

8:00 - 8:45 a.m.	Worship in Roman Catholicism Tradition	La Salle BC
9:00 - 10:00 a.m.	Plenary Session: Joseph P. Lucia	La Salle BC
10:00 - 10:30 a.m.	Exhibits Hall Opening	La Salle A & Le Salon
10:30 - 11:30 a.m.	(Library) Education of Desire	Poydras
	Assessing the Future of Educational Technology	La Salle BC
	Grant Assessment, Management, and Reporting	Acadian I
	NACO Listen and Learn Session	Acadian II
	New From Publishers - Fortress Press & Gorgias Press	Magnolia
	“Part of the Furniture”	Fulton
	WorldCat Discovery Services	Cypress
11:30 a.m. - 1:00 p.m.	CATLA Regional Meeting	Café 601
	SWATLA Regional Meeting	Café 601
	United Church of Christ Denominational Meeting	Café 601
	Wabash Colloquy Alumni Lunch *	TBA
1:00 - 2:00 p.m.	ATLA Business Meeting	La Salle BC
2:00 - 3:30 p.m.	Can Theological Libraries Manage Innovation & Failure?	Poydras
	EBSCO Databases and Services	Oak
	New Orleans Voodoo in Caribbean Context	Magnolia
	Small Libraries Getting Organized in the Archives	Fulton
	The Educationally Effective Library	Pelican II
	The Quest for Elusive Teaching Opportunities	Acadian I
	The Treasures We Keep (and Share)	Acadian II
	Where Do We Go From Here: Mentoring	Cypress
3:30 - 4:30 p.m.	Exhibits Reception / Poster Sessions	La Salle A & Le Salon
4:30 - 6:00 p.m.	And After Seminary / Partnering with the Parish	Oak
	Building a History: Stone-Campbell Movement	Fulton
	Librarian as Co-Teacher	La Salle B
	Network for Religious Studies at a Distance	Acadian II
	Open Access: Responding to a Looming “Serials Crisis”	Poydras
	Understanding and Serving Diverse Populations	Magnolia
	You Can’t Always “Just Google It”	Acadian I
6:00 - 7:00 p.m.	Denominational Meetings	
	Anglican	Poydras
	Baptist	Acadian I
	Campbell-Stone	Oak
	Lutheran	Fulton
	Methodist	Magnolia
	Presbyterian & Reformed	Acadian II
Roman Catholic	Pelican I	
6:30 - 8:00 p.m.	TBN 10th Anniversary Celebration	TBA

ALL ATTENDEES

* INVITE ONLY

8:00 A.M. - 8:45 A.M. WORSHIP
Worship service in the Roman Catholicism tradition.
Officiant: Fr. Nile Gross
Location: La Salle BC

9:00 A.M. - 10:00 A.M. PLENARY SESSION
Common Ends: Libraries, Imagination, & the Conflict of Values in the Digital Moment
For the better part of two decades, libraries have been subject to a series of “end times” narratives, the visions therein always premised upon the waning of print culture and the eventual demise of the physical book as an embodiment of knowledge and culture. In parallel to those apocalyptic narratives, there’s been a counter-trend that celebrates the renaissance of the library as a newly vital space – liberated from the constraints of physical collections and devoted to the discovery and creation of new knowledge and culture. This talk will examine both the anxiety and the promise within those conflicting visions and posits in response a set of abiding principles that can guide us toward a medium independent understanding of library mission at a moment when transformation is a reality not just a buzzword.
Speaker: Joseph P. Lucia, Dean, Temple University Libraries
Location: La Salle BC

10:00 A.M. - 10:30 A.M. EXHIBITS
Exhibit hall opening.
Location: La Salle A & Le Salon

10:30 A.M. - 11:30 A.M. EXHIBITOR SHOWCASE
New From Publishers - Fortress Press and Gorgias Press
Join two of the leading publishers of materials for religious and theological libraries for a conversation of new resources and services for your library. Fortress Press will share information about essential reference texts for 2014 and digital content delivery to libraries. Gorgias Press will share information about their new library affiliate program, which allows libraries to order at a wholesaler discount, as well as highlights from new projects that might be of interest in Biblical Studies. Session will include opportunities for questions and answers.
Presenters: Olga Lobasento and Rachel Shields
Location: Magnolia

10:30 A.M. - 11:30 A.M. EXHIBITOR SHOWCASE
WorldCat Discovery Services
Join OCLC’s Paul Cappuzzello for a WorldCat Discovery Services introduction. WorldCat Discovery Services provide a new suite of cloud-based applications that enables people to discover more than 1.5 billion electronic, digital and physical resources in your library and libraries around the world through a single search.
Presenter: Paul Cappuzzello
Location: Cypress

10:30 A.M. - 11:30 A.M. LISTEN AND LEARN SESSION
NACO
Attendees will discuss their use of authority records and what they consider to be best practices. There will also

be a discussion of new subfields and new interpretations of the fields.
Presenter: Judy Knop, NACO Funnel Coordinator, ATLA
Location: Acadian II

10:30 A.M. - 11:30 A.M. PANEL PRESENTATION
Grant Assessment, Management and Reporting: Lessons Learned from The Religion in North Carolina Grant Project
Participants in the Religion in North Carolina Digitization Project based at Duke will discuss the ins and outs of managing, reporting, and assessing a federally funded project. With regard to assessment, topics covered will include extracting statistical data from Internet Archive and using Qualtrics software for developing surveys and web-based metrics. Discussion will then turn to reporting and will cover techniques for the preparation of annual reports and multiple year renewal applications. Finally, focus will fall on grant management where the panel will highlight a variety of best practices related to the managing sub contracts, overseeing grant funded employees, observance of accounting rules, and interacting with an Office of Research Support and Office of Sponsored Programs. Time will be provided for questions and discussion.
Panelists: Phu Nguyen, Digitization and Technology Librarian; Beth Sheppard, Director; Shanee Yvette Murrain, Reference & Public Services Librarian; Elizabeth DeBold, Project Coordinator for the Religion in North Carolina Digitization Project, Duke University Divinity School Library
Location: Acadian I

10:30 A.M. - 11:30 A.M. PAPER
Assessing the Future of Educational Technology in Theological Education
Educational and Academic Technology have been part of the pedagogical landscape throughout the last hundred years, yet these terms have been popular in the lexicon of higher education much more recently as we’ve embraced the so-called “digital” or “Internet age.” The role of technologists has been on the rise as e-based and Internet learning, engagement, and pedagogy become more relevant to our academic worlds. This paper will examine both the development of educational technology and where it is going in theological education. Specifically, we will look at library trends, which incorporate technologists into their structural staff frameworks, as well as how leadership roles in educational technology have expanded or contracted within theological schools and seminaries, and what real future proposals may be made around this increasingly necessary field.
Presenter: Anthony J. Elia, Director of Library and Educational Technology, Christian Theological Seminary
Location: La Salle BC

10:30 A.M. - 11:30 A.M. PAPER
(Library) Education of Desire: James K. A. Smith’s Pedagogical Proposals and the Theological Library
What if the goal of Christian education was not to change what our students think but to change what they desire? Philosopher James K. A. Smith argues in his Cultural Liturgies trilogy that we should think of Christian higher education as teaching students to desire or love the right things. A task that involves paying close attention to physical practices and the imaginative narrative that informs them. This is a helpful paradigm to rethink the goals and processes of library instruction. This paper will unpack Smith’s argument, ask questions about how current student research practices may shape their desires, and how librarians can engage our student’s imaginations and promote healthy information practices.
Presenter: Matthew Ostercamp, Access Services Librarian, North Park University
Location: Poydras

10:30 A.M. - 11:30 A.M. PAPER
"Part of the Furniture": Family Bibles in Nation, Home, and Library

Most seminary and divinity libraries have at least several of these massive, folio size, ornamental, and richly illustrated family Bibles housed in their collections. Perhaps more are perpetually in cataloging backlog limbo as libraries put off decisions about what to do with them. Why were these Bibles produced? What cultural and technological factors lie behind their publishing history? Given their presence in our library collections, what treatment should they receive? This paper will look at the phenomenon of family Bibles in 19th century North America and offer a perspective concerning their retention, care, and instructional value in 21st century theological libraries.

Presenter: Bruce Eldevik, Reference and Special Collections Librarian, Luther Seminary
Location: Fulton

11:30 A.M. - 1:00 P.M. MEETING
CATLA Regional Meeting

Meeting of the Chicago Area Theological Library Association.
Location: Café 601 (601 Poydras Street, New Orleans, LA 70170)

11:30 A.M. - 1:00 P.M. MEETING
SWATLA Regional Meeting

Meeting of the Southwest Area Theological Library Association.
Location: Café 601 (601 Poydras Street, New Orleans, LA 70170)

11:30 A.M. - 1:00 P.M. MEETING
United Church of Christ Denominational Meeting

Meeting of the United Church of Christ Denominational group.
Location: Café 601 (601 Poydras Street, New Orleans, LA 70170)

11:30 A.M. - 1:00 P.M. SPECIAL SESSION
Wabash Colloquy Alumni Lunch

Alumni of the Wabash Center's Teaching and Learning Colloquy on The Role of Theological School Librarians (2000, 2004, 2007, 2010, and 2013 cohorts) are invited to gather for a reunion lunch.

Location: TBA

1:00 P.M. - 2:00 P.M. MEETING
ATLA Business Meeting

Board President Beth Bidlack will preside over this session, which includes the results of the Board election, an update from the Endowment Committee, an invitation to the 2015 Conference in Denver, and an open forum to discuss the proposal to increase Individual and Student Member dues.

President Presiding: Beth Bidlack

Location: La Salle BC

2:00 P.M. - 3:30 P.M. CONVERSATION GROUP
TLIG: The Quest for Elusive Teaching Opportunities: Some Specific Experiences

Like knights seeking the Holy Grail, Information Literacy librarians seek opportunities to teach. And like the Grail, those opportunities prove elusive, especially at institutions where there is no requirement for students to master an IL component. This session hopes to address the fundamental question of how one creates opportunities to teach by outlining

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Quakers and Abolition

Edited by
 BRYCCAN CAREY and
 GEOFFREY PLANK

Hardcover \$45.00; E-book

*Unjacketed

six serendipitous events that gradually evolved into formalized occasions for instruction at Bridwell Library, Perkins School of Theology. I will describe briefly what they are and how they came about, then open the session up for conversation about the practical experiences of other librarians.

Facilitators: Jane Elder, Reference Librarian, Bridwell Library, Southern Methodist University; Clair Powers, Instruction/E-Resources Librarian, Phillips Theological Seminary Library; Elizabeth A. Leahy, Professor of Theological Research and Bibliography Special Assistant to the Dean, University Libraries, Graduate School of Theology, Azusa Pacific University
Location: Acadian I

2:00 P.M. - 3:30 P.M. CONVERSATION GROUP

Where Do We Go From Here: Can Mentoring Be One Solution to Address the Shifting Cataloging Landscape?
Cataloging today can be a challenge. Standards are changing. Library users need immediate access. Rumors and realities of the semantic web arise in daily conversations. Catalogers must still provide metadata. Are new catalogers prepared to meet these challenges? Can small libraries adjust quickly to the rapid changes occurring? How do we provide metadata for users in the shifting cataloging landscape? One strategy to address the challenges of the changes in cataloging is through mentoring. This conversation will seek to determine how our collective knowledge can be leveraged through mentoring to tackle cataloging challenges today and tomorrow.

Facilitator: Donna Wells, Assistant Director, Southeastern Baptist Theological Seminary Library
Location: Cypress

2:00 P.M. - 3:30 P.M. EXHIBITOR SHOWCASE
EBSCO Databases and Services

Learn about EBSCO resources that will serve your library patrons' research needs. This session will focus on EBSCO Discovery Service, EBSCO eBooks, and the wide range of EBSCO religion database offerings.

Presenter: David Dubard
Location: Oak

2:00 P.M. - 3:30 P.M. IN-CONFERENCE WORKSHOP
The Educationally Effective Library: Addressing ATS Standard 4

A theological school accredited by the Association of Theological Schools (ATS) needs to demonstrate in detail how its library is a central resource for learning and scholarship. This workshop discusses the specific kinds of data and arguments that are necessary for librarians to craft a strong section in regards to ATS Standard 4 (library and information resources). The skills practiced in the workshop are also applicable to the ongoing work of advocating for the library within one's organization.

Presenter: Timothy D. Lincoln, Director of the Stitt Library, Austin Presbyterian Theological Seminary
Location: Pelican II

2:00 P.M. - 3:30 P.M. INTEREST GROUP PRESENTATION

WRIG: New Orleans Voodoo in Caribbean Context

Dr. Rosanne Adderley, Department of History, Tulane University will present a talk about how New Orleans voodoo fits in with Haitian Vodun, Santeria, and some other Caribbean religions.

Presenters: Dr. Laura Rosanne Adderley, Associate Professor, Department of History, African & African Diaspora Studies, School of Liberal Arts, Tulane University; Ellen Frost, Chair, World Religions Interest Group, Acquisitions Librarian, Bridwell Library, Perkins School of Theology, Southern Methodist University
Location: Magnolia

2:00 P.M. - 3:30 P.M. LISTEN AND LEARN SESSION

Small Libraries Getting Organized in the Archives: How Small Institutions Can Get Control Over Unlabeled Boxes

Small theological libraries tend to be connected to institutions with long histories. These histories tend to have been brought into the library's collection without any funding or time to process the collection. Utilizing student employees, minimal processing, and spreadsheets, mountains of unorganized paperwork can be realistically turned into a well-organized, weeded, and accessible collection. Other issues discussed will be archival use policies and preservation issues for the small library.

Presenters: Evan Boyd, Assistant Librarian, Chicago Theological Seminary; Susan Ebertz, Director of the Reu Library, Wartburg Theological Seminary
Location: Fulton

2:00 P.M. - 3:30 P.M. PANEL PRESENTATION

Can Theological Libraries Manage Innovation and Failure? Welcome to the Church of Fail

Failure is all around us in our libraries and institutions. How many of projects or programs have been failures for you, or you have heard the words "Epic Fail" uttered in a meeting? Picking up on current business literature, members of the first "Creating the Leaders of Tomorrow Cohort" will explore how failure is managed in libraries drawing on current literature and their personal experience. The panel will address issues such as whether failure is ignored, acknowledged, or perhaps even analyzed? Does failure make libraries risk-adverse? Should libraries be more like business start-ups even though most start-ups fail? How can libraries use failure to be more innovative? Can we create a "loop" for evaluating failure?

Panelists: Jennifer Bartholomew, Digital Resources Librarian, Luther Seminary; Suzanne Estelle-Holmer, Reference & Instructional Services Librarian, Yale Divinity School; Kris Veldheer, CEO, New Vistas Educational Consulting
Location: Poydras

2:00 P.M. - 3:30 P.M. PANEL PRESENTATION

The Treasures We Keep (and Share): Libraries and Archives in a Global Network

A network of international theological librarians and archivists presents promising opportunities for collecting, processing, promoting, and sharing information. This session introduces attendees to the current state and work of libraries with special collections and archival collections outside the North American context. The session also identifies promising opportunities and challenges facing global librarians including the exploration of collaborative possibilities for librarians and archivists throughout the world.

Panelists: Sabahat F. Adil, PhD Candidate and Editor for Golden Sage Editing, University of Chicago; Christopher J. Anderson, Head of Special Collections, University Archives, and Methodist Librarian, Drew University; Gareth Lloyd, Methodist Archivist, University of Manchester; Ukkamsa, Library Coordinator, Library

of *Sitagu Intl Buddhist Academy*; *Veronique Verspeurt, Librarian for the Faculty of Theology and Religious Studies, Maurits Sabbe Library, KU Leuven*; *Rev. Ephraim Mudave Kanguha, University Librarian, Africa International University*
 Location: *Acadian II*

EXHIBITS RECEPTION & POSTER SESSIONS

3:30 P.M. - 4:30 P.M.

Location: *La Salle A & Le Salon*

Research Instruction for Bible and Ministry Students using Problem-Based Learning Concepts

Describes a research instruction project launched as a result of faculty and librarian feeling that, while producing research papers containing citations from scholarly religion databases (e.g., *ATLASerials®*), too many undergraduates did not seem able to adequately handle the information within those articles. After a year's worth of library instruction emphasizing technical specifics of database searching, the author decided to experiment with problem-based learning (PBL) models for more effective research process and information literacy (IL) instruction.

Presenter: Justin Lillard, Reference Librarian, Harding University

Disaster Un-Preparedness

In October 2013, New Orleans Baptist Seminary John T. Christian Library experienced a water disaster involving the rare book collection, caused by an air conditioning unit. This poster presentation will follow library staff as we discovered, mitigated, and recovered in the months since.

Presenter: Kyara St. Amant, Head of Technical Services, New Orleans Baptist Theological Seminary

Spurgeon 2.0

The Spurgeon Library consists of the private collection of pastor and theologian, Charles Spurgeon. His library was acquired by Midwestern Baptist Theological Seminary in 2006. In the fall of 2012, a Twitter account was started in order to promote the collection to the academic Christian community and lay members of churches. This poster presentation will focus on how to have a successful Twitter account for a special collection. The presentation will highlight best practices in social media such as posting regularly, creating engaging themes, and having a clear strategy. The presentation will also give practical advice about how to increase followers on Twitter by following accounts that share similar interests to your archive. This presentation will emphasize certain tools and methods built within Twitter that allow users to make connections to specific people and organizations. The presenter will also instruct on accepted Twitter practices on how to communicate with followers. Also, the presentation will concentrate on what types of accounts on Twitter to avoid in order to maintain credibility to your account. This presentation will also highlight how to use and analyze statistics in order to determine premium times of posting in order to garner attention to your account. These statistics can also be used to determine the types of tweets that followers find engaging. The presenter will demonstrate how those tweets can be used in order to gain more attention to a special collection or archive.

Presenter: Robert Burgess, Head of Acquisitions, Midwestern Baptist Theological Seminary

Strategies, Tactics, and Secrecy in the Information Practices of the Underground Christian Communities in Modern China – A Collectivist Model

This poster presents a model to examine the information practices of the underground Christian communities in China from the perspective of social constructivism. This poster expands our understanding of the information practices of clandestine religious communities and

societies by exploring the information practices of the underground Protestant Christian communities in modern China. Using de Certeau's concepts of strategies and tactics in the practice of everyday life and Chatman's theories of small worlds and information poverty, as theoretical frameworks, I construct a conceptual model that explains how underground Protestant Christians in China seek and use religious information in secrecy.

Presenter: Cindy S Lu, Librarian for Asian Christianity, Yale Divinity Library

Developing a Student Tool Kit at Camden Theological Library, Australia

How a theological library in Australia developed a creative solution as one strategy to ensure students received quality support in the face of diminishing staff numbers.

Presenter: Gavin Glenn, Camden Theological Library, Uniting Church in Australia

4:30 P.M. - 6:00 P.M. CONVERSATION GROUP

Network for Religious Studies at a Distance

With the rise of distance programs, the issue of access to print library collections at a distance is becoming increasingly important. This discussion invites ATLA member libraries to discuss the creation of a network of college, university, and seminary libraries which will grant check out privileges to students in online, distance, and blended at other network schools. This discussion is intended to result in the creation of a network for the fall of 2014.

Facilitator: Thomas E. Phillips, Dean of Library, Claremont School of Theology

Location: Acadian II

4:30 P.M. - 6:00 P.M. CONVERSATION GROUP

Understanding and Serving Diverse Populations: The New Orleans Experience

New Orleans provides an excellent opportunity to introduce ATLA members to an interesting and diverse population in their local context. This conversation group will focus on helping ATLA members learn to understand and serve a multi-ethnic, multi-cultural population through dialogue with members of the New Orleans community who can apprise the group of the post-Katrina realities of New Orleans. Sponsored by the ATLA Diversity Committee, the goals of the conversation group are to develop intercultural competency and to encourage the development of ideas for new or improved library services that address the needs of diverse library users in the local context of the ATLA member libraries.

Facilitators: Lynn Berg, Librarian for Technical Services, New Brunswick Theological Seminary; Jaeyeon Lucy Chung, Library Director, United Library, Garrett-Evangelical Theological Seminary; Daniel F. Flores, Adjunct Instructor at Southern Methodist University, Perkins School of Theology

Location: Magnolia

4:30 P.M. - 6:00 P.M. CONVERSATION GROUP

You Can't Always "Just Google It": Helping Patrons Use the Print Collection

Not all of the useful materials our patrons need have been digitized. (We know this, but increasingly, our patrons do not realize it.) How can we counteract the

growing reliance on whatever can be “googled”? What can theological librarians do to help their students and faculty discover and benefit from the riches of our print collections? Do we need to change: how we provide reference help; How we enhance our catalog and create finding aids; How we communicate with our users about the existence and use of print materials; and how we train new staff? Come help us explore answers to these questions.

Facilitators: Lisa K. Grover, Technical Services Librarian, Denver Seminary; Elyse Hayes, Director of Library and Information Services, Seminary of the Immaculate Conception; James Humble, Assistant Library Director, Saint Charles Borromeo Seminary; Stephen Sweeney, Director of the Library, Saint John Vianney Theological Seminary

Location: Acadian I

4:30 P.M. - 6:00 P.M. PANEL PRESENTATION
Building a History: Linking the Special Collections of the Stone-Campbell Movement

This conversation group will explore projects being done by members of the Campbell-Stone denominational group. The specific focus will be on the attempts to collaborate in hopes of creating network of complementary projects.

Facilitators: Carisse Mickey Berryhill, Special Collections Librarian, Abilene Christian University; Don Meredith, Head Librarian, Harding School of Theology; Bob Turner, Circulation Librarian, Harding School of Theology; Chris Rosser, Oklahoma Christian University, Tamie Willis, Library Director, Oklahoma Christian University

Location: Fulton

4:30 P.M. - 6:00 P.M. PANEL PRESENTATION
Librarian as Co-Teacher: Information Literacy Embedded in Theology Courses

Two instances of embedded librarianship are presented in this panel discussion, both in Theology and Religious Studies courses fulfilling the undergraduate core requirement for students not necessarily majoring in Theology or Religious Studies. In one instance, the librarian collaborated with the discipline faculty member from coursework design to assessment, and appeared with the discipline faculty member in front of the classroom on a number of occasions. This course followed the traditional course model of lecture with a research project due at the end of the semester. In another course, the librarian appeared at the beginning of the semester for an orientation session, along the lines of the traditional “one shot” information literacy session, and then remained available for office hours. This course was structured along the lines of a science course, with class lecture days and a “lab day” to be spent in the library doing research. This panel, comprised of one librarian and two discipline faculty members, presents experiences, outcomes, and lessons learned. Attendees will learn two methods of integrating information literacy into coursework and appreciate both the benefits and pitfalls of this kind of collaboration.

Panelists: Martha Adkins, Assistant Professor, Reference Librarian, University of San Diego; Mark Bilby, Lecturer, University of San Diego; Patricia Plovanih, Assistant Professor, University of San Diego

Location: La Salle B

4:30 P.M. - 6:00 P.M. PANEL PRESENTATION
Open Access: Responding to a Looming “Serials Crisis” in Theological and Religious Studies

Over the last several years, librarians have watched as many reputable society and institution journals in theology and religion have been

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SAGE is pleased to support the ATLA Scholarships and Grant Funds and Support Members’ Participation in the Conference.

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acquired by commercial publishers. The common result is often an increase – sometimes a dramatic increase – in subscription price. Has the “serials crisis” finally found its way to theological and religious studies? How can libraries that are under increasing budget pressures respond? Cancel more journals? Buy less books? Some believe that open access, a publishing model which leverages low cost tools and the distribution/discovery power of the web, is a viable alternative. But how can we convince scholars, librarians, and their supporting institutions to get behind this alternative? In this panel presentation, the editors of *Theological Librarianship*, an online journal of the American Theological Library Association, draw on over six years of experience to talk about open access, addressing such issues as establishing quality and reputation, assuring sustainability, and encouraging libraries to get involved as promoters and publishers of open access journals.

Panelists: Gary F. Daught, Director of Library Services, Milligan College; Melody Layton McMahon, Director of the Library, Catholic Theological Union; David Stewart, Director of Libraries, Bethel University

Location: Poydras

4:30 P.M. - 6:00 P.M.

PAPER

And After Seminary – Where Does a Minister Go to Grow? // Partnering with the Parish: Information Behaviors of Faith Communities

“And After Seminary”

This paper intends to illustrate the need for the continuation of library services to ecumenical ministers after they have left seminary. This will involve a brief history of my experience as the Program Director and Librarian for the Sustaining Pastoral Excellence Program and Resource Center at St. Francis Retreat Center in DeWitt, Michigan, after having received a \$1.39 million grant from the Lilly Endowment, Inc. The question that needed to be addressed was “who ministers to the minister”? St. Francis Retreat Center decided that we would create an environment that was ecumenical – any and all Christian denominations would be welcome. All funding is now from individual and partner donations. This project could easily have just died out with the exception of some original thinking and the passion of those who were determined to have an ecumenical center available in the area. The melding of caring for those in ecumenical ministry by way of programming, peer groups, large group events, and a fully functioning resource center has created a unique experience for mid-Michigan.

Presenter: Terry Feuka, Program Director/Media Specialist, SPE at St. Francis Retreat Center

“Partnering with the Parish”

What is the role of information in a faith community? Are congregational practices of accessing, collecting, and sharing information sufficient for meeting their information needs? This paper seeks to answer these questions based on field observations of and reflections on the information behaviors of representative faith communities. A fuller understanding of information in congregational contexts has the potential to open up new possibilities for transformative practices of faith that can be enabled and supported by theological libraries.

Presenter: Myka Kennedy Stephens, Seminary Librarian, Lancaster Theological Seminary

Location: Oak

6:00 P.M. - 7:00 P.M.

MEETING

Denominational Group Meetings

Anglican.....Poydras
Baptist Acadian I
Campbell-Stone Oak
LutheranFulton
Methodist..... Magnolia
Presbyterian & Reformed..... Acadian II
Roman Catholic Pelican I

6:30 P.M. - 8:00 P.M.

SPECIAL SESSION

TBN 10th Anniversary Celebration

The Theological Book Network and ATLA invite you to celebrate TBN’s 10th anniversary along with 10 years of partnership between TBN and ATLA members. This event is jointly sponsored by TBN and ATLA.

Location: TBA

FRIDAY, JUNE 20

8:00 - 9:00 a.m.	ACLS Humanities E-Book	Oak
	Introduction to Christian Periodical Index	Cypress
	Librarians Managing Copyright	Pelican I
	Libraries & MOOCs	Acadian I
	New and Changed Subject Headings	Poydras
	Shrinking Budget, Expanding Selection	Acadian II
	Teaching Analytical Reading to Seminary Students	Pelican II
	The Foundations of Faith and Learning Integration	Fulton
9:15 - 10:15 a.m.	State of the Association	La Salle BC
10:15 - 11:00 a.m.	Exhibits Break	La Salle A & Le Salon
11:00 a.m. - 12:30 p.m.	A Forgotten Page: Women & Printing Industry	Poydras
	Collection Development Tools and Their Impact	Acadian I
	Connecting and Collaborating with Theological Libraries	Acadian II
	Core Competencies Conversation	Cypress
	Overcoming Technology Roadblocks Unconference	Oak
	Resources for Alums	Pelican II
	The Challenge of Library Space	Fulton
	What's Replacing Reference?	La Salle B
12:30 - 2:00 p.m.	ICC Lunch*	Magnolia
	NACO Lunch*	Audubon
2:00 - 3:00 p.m.	Blogging and Your Library	Fulton
	CONSER Conversation Group	Oak
	E-Book Lending Project	Poydras
	From Today's Users to Tomorrow's Vision	Acadian I
	New and Forthcoming Resources on theARDA.com	Acadian II
	The Introduction to Theological Bibliography & Research	La Salle B
	Yale's Historical Sound Recordings	Pelican II
3:00 - 3:30 p.m.	Exhibits Closing	La Salle A & Le Salon
4:45 - 5:45 p.m.	Plenary Session: Kathryn Reklis ◇	Leavell Chapel
5:45 - 6:30 p.m.	Worship in Baptist Tradition ◇	Leavell Chapel
6:30 - 8:30 p.m.	Reception at NOBTS ◇	The Hardin Student Center

ALL ATTENDEES

* INVITE ONLY

◇ OFF SITE: NEW ORLEANS BAPTIST
THEOLOGICAL SEMINARY CAMPUS

8:00 A.M. - 9:00 A.M. CONVERSATION GROUP***Librarians Managing Copyright***

In many academic institutions, librarians provide leadership in promoting compliance with copyright law. This conversation group will focus on how librarians can contribute to institutional policy formation and decision-making. Participants will be invited to share resources, challenges, and accomplishments.

Facilitator: Eileen K. Saner, Director of Library Services, Anabaptist Mennonite Biblical Seminary

Location: Pelican I

8:00 A.M. - 9:00 A.M. CONVERSATION GROUP***Teaching Analytical Reading to Seminary Students: A Followup Conversation***

This session is a follow-up conversation to the presentation at the 2013 Conference titled, "Teaching Analytical Reading Skills to Seminary Students." This conversation will enable participants to share ways they have found to utilize some of the ideas from the presentation, discuss difficulties, and brainstorm about other methods. If anyone wants to join this conversation who was not able to attend the 2013 presentation, they can read the article in the Conference *Proceedings* or they can e-mail me for copies of the materials.

Facilitator: Laura Harris, Reference & Instruction Librarian, Iliff School of Theology

Location: Pelican II

8:00 A.M. - 9:00 A.M. EXHIBITOR SHOWCASE***ACLS Humanities E-Book – Digital Resources in Academia***

This session will describe, compare, and analyze various digital resources, collections, and materials for use in academic settings and highlight the various digital programs available to librarians, faculty, and students in the social sciences, humanities, and related areas. This will include materials from publishers, societies, university presses, and aggregators. Attendees will learn about how these resources are collected, organized, and disseminated to users. This session will also include the titles in the Humanities e-Book collection as of 2014.

Presenters: Lee Walton and Ed Reiner

Location: Oak

8:00 A.M. - 9:00 A.M. EXHIBITOR SHOWCASE***Introduction to Christian Periodical Index***

Christian Periodical Index (CPI) is the preeminent index for researching a biblical worldview on a wide variety of topics. Published by the Association of Christian Librarians (ACL), CPI is available online from EBSCO and in print. CPI provides the only comprehensive index to articles and reviews from across the evangelical Christian perspective.

Presenters: Jamey Wilkes and Lori Thornton

Location: Cypress

8:00 A.M. - 9:00 A.M. LISTEN AND LEARN SESSION***Libraries & MOOCs***

Massively open online courses (MOOCs) are anticipated to become a prevailing alternative method to higher education. Regent University is launching a new MOOC platform that will broadly extend the concept to faith-focused institutions. The Regent University School of Divinity anticipates that this will provide new opportunities to train church leadership in areas around the world where such undertakings were previously cost prohibitive. The presenter is asking these questions and will share her research and first-hand experiences in hopes to encourage further conversation within the library community about librarians' role in MOOCs.

Presenter: Melody Diehl, Librarian for Religious Studies & Theology, Regent University

Location: Acadian I

8:00 A.M. - 9:00 A.M. LISTEN AND LEARN SESSION***New and Changed Subject Headings: How Does One Keep Up? Does One Even Try to Keep Up?***

The changes in subject headings required by RDA is just the tip of an iceberg. Subject headings have been added and changed for years. What do these changes – and, more importantly, keeping up with these changes – mean to catalogers, to instruction and information literacy librarians, and administrators? "Prayer" used to imply "Christianity"; now "Prayer – Christianity" is specifically for Christian prayer, while "Prayer" is a generic subject heading. The subdivision "– Doctrinal and controversial works" was dropped as a subject heading, replaced by "– Doctrines" and "Controversial Literature." A computer cannot easily make the conversion from one form to another – certainly not as easily as "Bible. N.T. Matthew" becoming "Bible. Matthew." How important is the maintenance of our metadata? Is the time and effort spent in creating the metadata in the first place being lost because of lack of maintenance? Should we worry about changes – or not? Should our patrons simply be told "Look for your subject under these two (or three or four) possibilities"? This Listen and Learn Session will allow time to consider and respond to these concerns.

Presenter: Richard A. Lammert, Technical Services Librarian, Concordia Theological Seminary

Location: Poydras

8:00 A.M. - 9:00 A.M. LISTEN AND LEARN SESSION***Shrinking Budget, Expanding Selection: Patron-Driven Acquisition at Trinity International University***

Electronic books (e-books) offer theological libraries the opportunity to tailor their e-collections to meet the demands of students and faculty through patron-driven acquisition (PDA) programs. Trinity International University's Roling Library introduced ebrary in December 2012. In the remaining six months of the 2012-2013 fiscal year, ebrary e-book purchases accounted for over 10% of the library's total book budget; 13% of these purchases were PDA titles. The percentage of PDA titles is growing in the 2013-2014 fiscal year, as some liaisons are now investing the majority of their funds into the PDA program. How does PDA affect Roling Library's finances? What percentage of PDA titles is being purchased in the current fiscal year, and how are these titles being used? What are the most popular subjects? Has the expansion of the program indeed resulted in a greater percentage of PDA purchases? This presentation explores the PDA program at Roling Library, reports relevant statistics and their impact on future collection development strategies, and elucidates the collection management staff's workflow.

Presenter: Stephanie Fletcher, Collection Management Librarian, Trinity International University

Location: Acadian II

8:00 A.M. - 9:00 A.M. PAPER***The Foundations of Faith and Learning Integration at Calvin and Wheaton***

Wheaton College, with roots in the American Protestant evangelical tradition, and Calvin College, with roots in the Dutch Reformed tradition, have worked hard to encourage distinctively Christian higher education and scholarship. This co-authored paper provides a comparative history

of the integration of faith and learning at Wheaton and Calvin, identifying the key figures and their contributions to the design and content of their respective programs, and providing annotated bibliographic background. The authors will also offer comments on the current life and trajectory of faith and learning in Christian [evangelical] higher education and its impact on their respective libraries.

Presenters: Greg Morrison, Assistant Professor of Library & Information Science, Wheaton College; Lugene Schemper, Theological Librarian, Calvin College

Location: Fulton

9:15 A.M. – 10:15 A.M.

Change is in the Air: The State of the Association

Executive Director Brenda Bailey-Hainer will provide an update on the activities and accomplishments of ATLA during the past year and outline changes for the coming year which will more closely align Association resources with achieving ATLA's Mission and Organizational Ends.

Presenter: Brenda Bailey-Hainer, ATLA Executive Director

Location: La Salle BC

10:15 A.M. – 11:00 A.M.

EXHIBITS BREAK

Location: La Salle A & Le Salon

11:00 A.M. – 12:30 P.M.

CONVERSATION GROUP

Core Competencies Conversation

This conversation follows up on a Core Competencies panel in 2012 and a Core Competencies Conversation in 2013 by identifying the key elements in a draft of a statement of core competencies and/or credentials useful to ATLA members in recruiting or developing well-qualified theological librarians.

Facilitators: Carisse Mickey Berryhill, Associate Dean, Special Collections Librarian, Abilene Christian University, Brown Library; Andrew J. Keck, Director, Luther Seminary Library

Location: Cypress

11:00 A.M. – 12:30 P.M.

INTEREST GROUP PRESENTATION

ETIG: Overcoming Technology Roadblocks Unconference

Following an unconference format, several participants will give brief presentations on their most difficult current or recent tech problem, including how they are working around it or think they might solve it. Participants will be encouraged to collaborate on solving the problem and share advice...etc. Suggestions for talks will be solicited before hand, and examples provided based on particular applications or use cases, if necessary, to encourage participation by a range of people. A short business meeting for ETIG will be held at the end of the session.

Presenters: Lisa Gonzalez, Electronic Resources Librarian, Catholic Theological Union; Robert Presutti, Curator of Archives and Manuscripts, Pitts Theology Library, Candler School of Theology, Emory University

Location: Oak

11:00 A.M. – 12:30 P.M.

PANEL PRESENTATION

CEAD: Collection Development Tools and Their Impact on Workflow and Library Acquisitions Budgets

This panel will explore tools used to evaluate and develop library collections, including their impact on workflow and library budgets. The panel includes a librarian who uses these tools, a Technical Services librarian, and a library director. Acquisitions personnel, librarians responsible for collection development, and library directors should all benefit from ideas presented. The Collection Evaluation and Development (CEAD) Interest Group meeting will take place at the end of the presentation.

Panelists: Leslie Engelson, Metadata Librarian, Murray State University; Dr. Dennis Swanson, Vice President for Library and Educational Assessment, The Master's Seminary

Location: Acadian I

11:00 A.M. – 12:30 P.M.

PANEL PRESENTATION

WCIG: Connecting and Collaborating with Theological Libraries Overseas

Join the World Christianity Interest Group for two presentations on experiences with theological libraries overseas. Sandy Ayer will share about his time in Cameroon, where he'll be serving as a librarian member of a consulting team whose mission is to help a group from Bangui, Central African Republic, start a teacher training college. Melody Layton McMahon's will share information about her experiences with Catholic Theological Libraries in Asia.

Panelists: Sandy Ayer, Director of Library Services, Ambrose Seminary; Melody Layton McMahon, Director of the Library, Catholic Theological Union; Filomena Saxton, University of Arizona

Location: Acadian II

11:00 A.M. – 12:30 P.M.

PANEL PRESENTATION

PSIG: Resources for Alums

What role does the library play in offering services to alums, and how does this role intersect with the offerings of other units in the theological institution? This panel will describe resources and services as they are offered at three different types of theological institutions. The session will begin with a brief business meeting for the Public Services Interest Group.

Panelists: James Darlack, Assistant Librarian for Reference & Bibliographic Instruction, Gordon-Conwell Theological Seminar; Tracy Powell Iwaskow, Head of Public Services and Periodicals Librarian, Pitts Theology Library, Candler School of Theology, Emory University; Karl Stutzman, Assistant Director, Digital Library Services, Anabaptist Mennonite Biblical Seminary

Location: Pelican II

11:00 A.M. – 12:30 P.M.

PANEL PRESENTATION

The Challenge of Library Space: the Experience of Planning and Dealing with a Renovated or Brand New Library Space

This presentation will address issues involved in planning, implementing, and dealing with changes to the library space configuration. Topics covered will include the rationale for re-configuring library space; making the decision whether to renovate the current space, move to a new space, or build an entirely new library; planning a renovation, new construction or move; and dealing with the consequences of a newly renovated or brand new space. The three panelists will relate their own experiences and time will be available for questions and comments from the audience.

Panelists: M. Patrick Graham, Margaret A. Pitts Professor of Theological Bibliography and Director, Pitts Theology Library, Candler School of Theology, Emory University; Andrew G. Kadel, Library Director, The Christoph Keller, Jr. Library, General Theological Seminary; Sandy Leach, Associate Director, Lineberger

Memorial Library, Lutheran Theological Southern Seminary/ Lenoir-Rhyne University; Amy Limpitlaw, Head Librarian, Boston University School of Theology Library
 Location: Fulton

11:00 A.M. - 12:30 P.M.

PANEL PRESENTATION

What's Replacing Reference? New Models for Information Services

Reference work has changed dramatically over the past five years. Online programs have transformed the way librarians deliver resources and instruction. Technology is transforming the way we communicate with faculty and students and new models of library service are changing the way we staff our libraries. Are we embedded librarians, personal, liaison, subject, or outreach librarians? Or all of the above? The panelists will discuss their experiences with new modes of delivering reference services on line and in person.

Panelists: Jennifer Bartholomew, Electronic Services Librarian, Luther Seminary; Suzanne Estelle-Holmer, Reference & Instructional Services Librarian, Yale University Divinity School Library; Shanee Yvette Murrain, Reference & Public Services Librarian, Duke University Divinity School Library

Location: La Salle B

11:00 A.M. - 12:30 P.M.

PAPER

A Forgotten Page: Women and the Sixteenth-Century Printing Industry

The role of women in the production of early printed books is often overlooked, but many printing presses in the sixteenth century were owned and operated by women and it was fairly common for a woman to continue the operation of a press after the death of her husband. The development of printing arguably had a greater impact on social and cultural change than any other industry during the Renaissance and Reformation and women played an important role in this central aspect of the sixteenth-century economy.

Presenter: Armin Siedlecki, Pitts Theology Library, Candler School of Theology, Emory University

Location: Poydras

12:30 P.M. - 2:00 P.M.

ICC Lunch

*By Invitation Only

Location: Magnolia

12:30 P.M. - 2:00 P.M.

NACO Lunch

*By Invitation Only

Location: Audubon

2:00 P.M. - 3:00 P.M.

CONVERSATION GROUP

Blogging and Your Library

Whether you are thinking about blogging or have been blogging on behalf of your library for some time, come join a conversation group with librarians who enjoy blogging to promote collections and activities of their libraries. Learn about tips and resources and from each other's experiences.

Facilitator: Liz Leahy, Professor, Theological Bibliography & Research, Azusa Pacific University

Location: Fulton

2:00 P.M. - 3:00 P.M.

CONVERSATION GROUP

The Introduction to Theological Bibliography and Research: The Past, Present, and Future of a Genre

The works of Barber/Krauss, Bollier/Stewart, Pazmino, and Yaghjian, are among the more recent examples of introductions to theological bibliography and research. Although diverse in their particular features,

these works bear a resemblance to each other in the ways that they introduce their audiences to theological reading, research, and writing. This conversation group will discuss what are the most helpful books in this genre (not limited to the examples listed above), identifying both enduring strengths, and also needed improvements or new options within the changing contexts of religious and theological studies.

Facilitator: John B. Weaver, Dean of Library and Educational Technology, Abilene Christian University

Location: La Salle B

2:00 P.M. - 3:00 P.M.

EXHIBITOR SHOWCASE

New and Forthcoming Resources on theARDA.com

After a brief review of the many free resources available on the Association of Religion Data Archives (theARDA.com), this session will introduce forthcoming and recent additions to the ARDA's Learning Center. The new resources include interactive family trees for world religions, new GIS services, lesson plans for instructors, new learning modules, new data collections, and an interactive historical timeline. The ARDA was selected as one of the 30 Best Free Reference Websites by the Reference and User Services Association of the ALA.

Presenters: Kevin D. Dougherty and Robert Martin

Location: Acadian II

2:00 P.M. - 3:30 P.M.

LISTEN AND LEARN SESSION

CONSER Conversation Group

Participants will discuss the latest CONSER Operations Committee Meeting decisions and Best Practices decided by CONSER members.

Facilitator: Judy Knop, Metadata Curator, ATLA

Location: Oak

2:00 P.M. - 3:00 P.M.

LISTEN AND LEARN SESSION

E-Book Lending Project: Formation and Progress Report

Come learn about the formation and progress of a new ambitious collaborative project that has the goal of providing opportunities for ATLA libraries to purchase to permanently own religious and theological e-books (not license access to them through a distributor or aggregator) for our circulating collections. You will meet the cast of Project & Team Leaders, find out how you can be involved, and hear about the project's progress and future plans.

Facilitator: Donna Campbell, Technical Services and System Librarian, Westminster Theological Seminary

Location: Poydras

2:00 P.M. - 3:00 P.M.

PAPER

From Today's Users to Tomorrow's Vision

As we imagine the libraries of tomorrow, we must listen to the library users of today. How can we do that effectively? And what might the users of today tell us about our future? This paper will explore how recent trends in studying library users help us listen in new ways. Are there times when we should ignore our current constituents in order to pursue more bold visions? Do we really need surveys and focus groups? We'll talk about engaging our stakeholders in new ideas for our shared future.

Presenter: Laura C. Wood, Director of Tisch Library,

Tufts University

Location: Acadian I

2:00 P.M. - 3:00 P.M.

PAPER

Yale's Historical Sound Recordings of the Christschall Label

This presentation will concentrate on a rare record label titled Christschall. This was a German label which focused on sacred music. The recordings are very rare; however Yale's Historical Sound Recording Collection is "blessed" with thirty-two 78 rpm recordings on this label. These are the only holdings outside of New Zealand, Germany, and Catalunya listed on OCLC. Yale's holdings are the largest grouping on OCLC and therefore possibly the largest collection in the world. Estimated to be recorded between 1927 and 1931 composers include Palestrina, Obrecht, Praetorius, Schubert, and Mozart. Gregorian chant and Epiphany music are among the types of music recorded on Christschall. Featured performers include the choirs of the Benedictine Abbey of Maria Laach, as well as Stephansdom in Vienna. The presentation would focus on the rarest pieces on these recordings.

Presenter: Diane Napert, Catalog Librarian, Divinity Library, Yale University

Location: Pelican II

3:00 P.M. - 3:30 P.M.

EXHIBITS CLOSING

Passport winners announced.

Location: La Salle A & Le Salon

AFTERNOON AND EVENING ON CAMPUS ◇

Attendees should meet at the front of the hotel at 3:45 p.m. for a bus transfer to the New Orleans Baptist Theological Seminary

4:45 P.M. - 5:45 P.M.

PLENARY SESSION

Tweet if You Want Tenure? New Media and the "New Academy"

Amidst concerns about the "decline of the liberal arts" and demands to make academic research and teaching more relevant to the real world are parallel prophesies of a "new academy" – one driven by new technologies of the digital age. Some greet the digital with eschatological hope, some with apocalyptic doom. Drawing on both her experiences using digital platforms in her scholarship and teaching, and her research studying the use of digital technologies by Christian communities, Kathryn Reklis will discuss the promises and challenges of new media in the academic study of religion.

Speaker: Kathryn Reklis, Assistant Professor, Department of Theology at Fordham University

Location: New Orleans Baptist Theological Seminary, Leavell Chapel

5:45 P.M. - 6:30 P.M.

WORSHIP

Worship at New Orleans Baptist Theological Seminary and Tours

Worship service in the Baptist tradition.

Speaker: Dr. Lloyd Harsch

Location: New Orleans Baptist Theological Seminary, Leavell Chapel

6:30 P.M. - 8:30 P.M.

RECEPTION

Reception at New Orleans Baptist Theological Seminary and Tours

Location: New Orleans Baptist Theological Seminary, The Hardin Student Center

Attendees should meet outside The Hardin Student Center at 8:30 p.m. for a bus transfer to the InterContinental New Orleans.

SATURDAY, JUNE 21

8:00 - 9:00 a.m.	Collaborative Student Research with Google Drive	Acadian II
	Contemporary Religious Literature Conversation Group	Oak
	Discovery and Acquisitions in Theological Libraries	Magnolia
	Preserving and Sharing Meditations of Howard Thurman	Fulton
	Supporting the Mission of the Institution	Acadian I
	The Final Frontier: Events and Hospitality	La Salle B
9:15 - 10:15 a.m.	English Parish Churches	Fulton
	Inventory - On a Dime and On Time	Cypress
	Library Orientation in a New Era	Pelican II
	MarcEdit 101 and Beyond	Oak
	Preparing Librarians for Changes in Classroom Instruction	Poydras
	That All May Learn	Acadian I
	What Would Jesus Hack?	Acadian II
10:30 - 11:30 a.m.	Worship in the Assemblies of God Tradition	La Salle BC
11:30 - 12:30 p.m.	Memorials and Conference Closing	La Salle BC

ALL ATTENDEES

THE ANTIOCH BIBLE

THE SYRIAC PESHITTA BIBLE WITH ENGLISH TRANSLATION

THE SYRIAC PESHITTA is one of the earliest versions of Scripture, and is the only version written in a Semitic setting, in a dialect of Aramaic. It contains many distinctive readings that are absent in other versions. The Syriac Old Testament probably originated as a Jewish targum ('translation'), that was inherited by the Aramaic-speaking Early Church, and is rich with links to the ancient Jewish exegetical tradition. The New Testament, in particular the Gospels, is a revision of an earlier Syriac version that dates to the early centuries of the Common Era.

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8:00 A.M. - 9:00 A.M. CONVERSATION GROUP
Contemporary Religious Literature Conversation Group

A time for conference attendees to share books they've read during the past year. Attendees often reflect on religious themes of what they are reading. All types of genres are open for discussion.

Facilitators: Jennifer Ulrich, Technical Service Librarian, Eastern Mennonite University; Donna Wells, Assistant Directory, Southeastern Baptist Theological Seminary

Location: Oak

8:00 A.M. - 9:00 A.M. CONVERSATION GROUP
Supporting the Mission of the Institution

"Support of the mission" is often a criterion for review, especially in institutions of higher education, and can be an ambiguous one to fulfill. This conversation group will present the opportunity for librarians at theological institutions to discuss how our work supports the missions of our institutions. Participants are encouraged to bring the mission statements of their institutions (and libraries, if they exist), and to come ready to share experiences, anxieties, and advice.

Facilitator: Martha Adkins, Assistant Professor, Reference Librarian, University of San Diego

Location: Acadian I

8:00 A.M. - 9:00 A.M. LISTEN AND LEARN SESSION
Collaborative Student Research with Google Drive: Advantages and Challenges

During the 2013-2014 academic year, the presenter and University of San Diego's theology librarian tried a pedagogical experiment that relied heavily on Google Drive. Its shared spaces and associated applications served a variety of purposes, especially research collaboration between students and between students and the professor. Placed in research working groups across sections, students augmented and annotated shared bibliographies in Google doc format. Notes often included local call numbers, loan status, links to e-books or full-text articles, and specific feedback about the research value of each source. Into a shared, personal Google drive folder, each student (and the professor as a fellow/model researcher) uploaded weekly research notes, a three-slide presentation, and an accompanying 100-word presentation. Thus students benefited from seeing the research and presentations of others throughout the semester and, in effect, constantly challenged each other to do better work each week. The implementation of Google Drive, however, took considerable time and energy and presented issues regarding sharing permissions (especially from spam filters that prevented sharing with a lot of e-mail addresses), space limitations, and even, surprisingly, student usability.

Presenter: Mark Bilby, University of San Diego

Location: Acadian II

8:00 A.M. - 9:00 A.M. LISTEN AND LEARN SESSION
Preserving and Sharing Meditations of Howard Thurman: Digitization and Transcription of Audio Archives at the Pitts Theology Library

In 2013, the Pitts Theology Library embarked on a project to digitize and transcribe audio archives. The project

began with cassettes of meditations by Howard Thurman, part of a gift donated to the library. These meditations have been digitized and are undergoing manual and automatic transcription through the use of software, volunteers, and library staff. In this session, I introduce the project and the process of preserving the audio and making the material available to public patrons. The process has been developed using many readily-available and open-source tools, most of which have been acquired for free or at little cost to the library. Software tools to be demonstrated include Audacity, InqScribe, and products from Nuance Software including Mac Speech Scribe and Dragon Dictate. I will also introduce the potential to crowdsource parts of the transcription project, including the development of a public tool for hearing and transcribing the Thurman meditations through the adaptation of open-source applications like Omeka and Scripto.

Presenter: Richard Manly Adams, Jr., Systems and Reference Librarian, Pitts Theology Library, Candler School of Theology, Emory University

Location: Fulton

8:00 A.M. - 9:00 A.M. PANEL PRESENTATION
Discovery and Acquisitions in Theological Libraries: A Conversation with University Presses

In 2008, AAUP surveyed academic librarians about what publishers' communication and marketing tools were most useful in making their collections decisions. Since then, there have been many changes on both sides of the book acquisitions equation: from new digital sales tools and greater e-book availability from presses; to transitions in acquisitions models and preferred communications channels by libraries. This session will open up a discussion about the tools university presses use to inform the library market, and how theological libraries discover and make acquisitions decisions about university press content.

Panelists: Patrick Alexander, Director, Penn State University Press; Carey Newman, Director, Baylor University Press

Location: Magnolia

8:00 A.M. - 9:00 A.M. PAPER
The Final Frontier: Events and Hospitality in the Theological Library Context

According to a 2012 review of the trends and issues affecting academic libraries in higher education produced by ACRL, one of the 10 challenges facing libraries is communicating value. As more and more resources have become available digitally, the ways in which libraries have traditionally filled their missions must be re-examined and libraries may need to adapt – even beyond shifts to creative commons models. Theological libraries can foster value by following the example of public library systems which offer programs tailored to meet the local community's cultural, economic and political needs. In short, the challenges we face as we assert the importance of the library in academic enterprise boil down to our ability to provide superior "service" in the academic area and beyond. This paper will focus first on theoretical and managerial aspects of transitioning a traditional "academic library" to a programming driven model. Then attention will turn to Duke Divinity School Library's exploration of this final frontier through offering student and faculty research centered programming that includes special speakers, faculty book signings, interest based social clubs, film screenings, and connections with internal and external constituents to stimulate student engagement, increase institutional visibility, and undergird learning outside the classroom.

Presenters: Beth M. Sheppard, Library Director, Duke Divinity School Library; Shaneé Murrain, Reference and Public Services Librarian, Duke Divinity School Library

Location: Pelican I

9:15 A.M. - 10:15 A.M. CONVERSATION GROUP***TSIG: MarcEdit 101 and Beyond***

The MarcEdit 101 workshop at last year's conference helped beginning users of MarcEdit understand the basics of how to use the program. An unexpected benefit of that workshop was the additional knowledge gained when those attending the workshop shared their tricks and techniques. This conversation group is an opportunity for users of MarcEdit to build upon that beginning opportunity by sharing what we have learned over the past year as we have implemented MacrEdit into our local workflow.

Facilitator: Leslie Engelson, Metadata Librarian, Murray State University

Location: Oak

9:15 A.M. - 10:15 A.M. LISTEN AND LEARN SESSION***Inventory - On a Dime and On Time***

Want to know that you have what your catalogue says you have where you say you have it? Many ILS's don't have an inventory module or require that you do the entire collection at once. We did an inventory using only a circulation scanner, a tablet, and a spreadsheet program. This session outlines the steps for the inventory including creating a shelf-list, using ILL's review file function, importing it into Excel, using advanced features, such as filters and conditional formatting to find errors, missing books, and unlinked barcodes. Each section of 2000-2400 records could be scanned in a little over an hour. Importing records into Excel and applying the filters and formatting take only 20 minutes, less with practice.

Presenter: Meagan Morash, Director of Library Services, Booth University College

Location: Cypress

9:15 A.M. - 10:15 A.M. LISTEN AND LEARN SESSION***Library Orientation in a New Era: A Transition in Progress, Continuing the Conversation***

Fall 2013 was the first year that Anabaptist Mennonite Biblical Seminary required a hybrid introductory course for all new MDiv students, both residential and distance. The course began with two weeks of online learning activities, continued with a week-long campus intensive and concluded with several more weeks of online work. Library assignments in the hybrid course opened opportunities to integrate information literacy into AMBS courses throughout the curriculum. A description of the Library's use of Moodle and LibGuides will be followed by group discussion of various options for library instruction.

Presenter: Eileen K. Saner, Director of Library Services, Anabaptist Mennonite Biblical Seminary

Location: Pelican II

9:15 A.M. - 10:15 A.M. LISTEN AND LEARN SESSION***Preparing Librarians for Changes in Classroom Instruction!***

A brief overview of some of the changes that are taking place in the classroom, such as: different ways of presenting content, the changing role of the instructor, gaining student feedback, allowing more student choices, using techniques to engage learners, and using higher-level cognitive objectives. An understanding of these changes will help librarians better serve the needs of both students and faculty in the future.

Presenter: Ken Boyd, University Instructional Designer, Taylor University

Location: Poydras

The ATLA Scholarships and Grants Fund

Thank you to EBSCO and the generous supporters of the ATLA Scholarship and Grants Fund. Listed below are individuals who donated to the fund during the period from July 2013-May 2014.

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9:15 A.M. - 10:15 A.M. PANEL PRESENTATION
That All May Learn: Three Approaches to In-House Professional Development

In our profession there is always more to learn, and there is never enough money. This leads many librarians to develop local, self-designed educational programs for staff. In this panel, three librarians will present approaches they have tried: creation of a learning community in the form of a departmental leadership team, use of a mentoring model for orientation of new staff, and implementation of the “21 Things” technology skill-building program. Each case will include success stories and cautionary tales, and the session will include ample time for Q&A and discussion.

Presenters: Miranda Bennett, Head of Liaison Services for Collections & Research Support, University of Houston Libraries; Michelle Spomer, Head of Stamps Library, Azusa Pacific University
Location: Acadian I

9:15 A.M. - 10:15 A.M. PAPER
English Parish Churches: Architectural Styles in Specific Churches Represented in the Collection of Pitts Theology Library

This paper will provide an overview of the types of material found in the Pitts Theology Library’s “Rev. Gordon Taylor Collection of English Church Histories” and also will focus specifically on several of the really outstanding churches and cathedrals represented in the collection.

Presenter: Denise Marie Hanusek, Cataloging Librarian, Pitts Theology Library, Candler School of Theology, Emory University
Location: Fulton

9:15 A.M. - 10:15 A.M. PAPER
What Would Jesus Hack? The Maker Movement, Maker Spaces, and Theological Libraries

One of the crucial tasks facing the contemporary Christian church and individual Christians is the relationship between theology and technology, that is, between Christian understandings of faith and understandings of technology. Can we put the words “God” and “technology” together in any kind of meaningful sentence, let alone a meaningful way of life? One emerging and potentially compelling approach to this question is the potential relationship between Christianity and the contemporary “hacker” or “maker” movement, which is a contemporary subculture focused on technology-based approaches to “do-it-yourself” collaboration, fabrication, and distribution of creative projects. With due attention to critiques of this approach, the paper will explore the metaphor of God as “hacker,” or “maker,” as well as the potential similarities between Christian beliefs/practices and those of many hackers/makers, e.g., commitment to principled practices of creation, alteration, and openness. This theological understanding of the “maker movement” will provide a basis for exploring the role of the theological library as a “maker space.”

Presenters: Amelia Carnagey, Undergraduate Student, Department of Art and Design, Abilene Christian University; Megan May, Instruction and Outreach Librarian, Abilene Christian University; John B. Weaver, Dean of Library Services and Educational Technology, Abilene Christian University
Location: Acadian II

10:30 A.M. - 11:30 A.M. WORSHIP

Worship service held in the Assemblies of God tradition.

Officiant: Dr. Teresa Reiger
Location: La Salle BC

11:30 A.M. - 12:30 P.M. MEMORIALS

Location: La Salle BC

12:30 P.M. CONFERENCE CLOSING

Speaker: Brenda Bailey-Hainer, Executive Director, ATLA
Location: La Salle BC

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LA SALLE BALLROOM B/C (ALL CONFERENCE SESSIONS)

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- 8
- 7
- 6
- 5
- 4
- 3
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9

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